

EXPLORING TIMBRE SPACES WITH TWO MULTIPARAMETRIC CONTROLLERS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the development so far of a system that uses multiparametric controllers along with an interactive high-level search process to navigate timbre spaces. Either of two previously developed interfaces are used as input devices; a hand tracking system and a malleable foam controller. Both interfaces share the property of streaming continuous multiparametric codependent data. When these data streams are mapped to synthesis parameters, the controllers can be used to explore the parameter space in an embodied manner; with the hand tracker, moving or changing the shape of the hand changes the sound, and with the foam, deforming its shape changes the sound. The controllers become too sensitive with larger parameter spaces, so a navigation system was developed to enable high level control over the subset of the parameter space in which the controllers are working. By moving and refining the working range, a timbre space can be progressively explored to find a desired sound. The search process was developed by focusing on three scenarios, the control of four, ten and forty dimensional timbre spaces. The system is used bi-manually, while one hand is used for detailed search with one of the input devices, the other hand controls high level search parameters with MIDI and the computer keyboard.

Initial reactions from two musicians indicate the development so far to be successful, the next stage in this project is to carry out formal user studies.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper explores the application of two multiparametric controllers as tools for timbre space navigation, and the development of high-level search strategies to complement their use in this context.

A previous study with an EchoFoam controller [1], a malleable foam interface, showed its potential for exploring timbre spaces. During the study, the controller was set up to navigate preset fixed subsets of a six-dimensional phase modulation synthesis patch. The participants manipulated the foam controller in order to change the synthesis parameters, in effect exploring the sound haptically. The results suggested it would be interesting to test high-level strategies for controlling the subset of parameter space within

which the controller was working, in order to help the user explore the full space more effectively. The results from the study also showed some participants perceiving the controller as producing slightly unpredictable or imprecise output, so imposing a larger controllable constraint onto its output could complement it well, making an interesting combination of order and unpredictability.

Another controller developed by the author, Phalanger [2], shares similar low level properties to the foam controller of continuously streaming codependent multiparametric control data. Phalanger is a computer vision based hand tracking system, that outputs hand geometry data for musical control. It was decided to include both controllers in the development process, with the aim of creating a timbre space navigation engine that would accept input from either controller, opening up some interesting opportunities for comparing these two opposing styles of tangible and intangible interaction.

The project was approached with the following questions in mind:

1. Is it possible to navigate subsets of a timbre space and gradually zoom in to the sound you are searching for?
2. How do these two controllers and this approach compare to conventional editing tools such as a GUI or knobs and sliders?
3. What are the differences between the two types of controller in this context?
4. Will this process plug in to any synthesis process? i.e. is it possible to explore any continually controllable synthesis algorithm without knowledge of its underlying workings?

This paper describes the progress so far on this project, which has been developed to the point where the first formal evaluation is about to start. The development process that addressed the above questions will be described, but first the motivations behind the project are explored.

2. MOTIVATION

Djajadiningrat et. al [3] take the view that the body is typically neglected in interaction:

‘Current interfaces indeed seem to be built on the assumption that interaction can be captured

in schemata and that the body is merely a mechanical executor. This view, however, does not do justice to our embodiment in the world.'

Extending this theme to the use of the hand for creativity in interaction, Treadaway [4] observes that current digital technology is 'deficient in utilising bodily intelligence'.

Exploring the use of bodily intelligence for controlling digital music tools is the main motivation for this project. The two controllers used here take an embodied approach to musical control compared to conventional interfaces such as the mouse and GUI or knobs and sliders. These conventional interfaces are typically up front, presenting their function to the user and enabling direct control of parameters. In contrast, these two interfaces output parallel streams of codependent parameters, and the user is required to employ their perceptual-motor skills to explore how the interface and mappings will function. This use of perceptual-motor skills is at the core of playing acoustic music where an embodied relationship with an instrument is fundamental to creating music with it. Conventional digital music interfaces in contrast can lack this embodied interaction, having more akin to scientific tools.

Further to this, another motivation is to explore accuracy and unpredictability of control. Gelineck and Serafin [5] commented on this issue in their survey of electronic musicians. 16 of 18 of the musicians they interviewed said they preferred tools that they don't fully understand or are unpredictable in some way. The two interfaces used in this project have accuracy proportional to the skill of the user and were perceived in previous studies by some users as unpredictable and imprecise compared to conventional controllers. It's compelling to see how this style of interaction can fit into the more precise world of digital music by imposing a structured framework on them. By applying these two controllers to the task of timbre space navigation, this issue can be explored further.

3. RELATED WORK

In [3], Djajadiningrat et. al. explore the use of multiparametric interfaces, suggesting these interfaces increase the bandwidth of interaction, allowing them to exploit motor skills for more sophisticated control. Focusing on music, Wanderley and Depalle [6] propose that control with multiple continuous parameters provides a more musical way of interacting with computers, moving towards the goal of control subtlety similar to acoustic instruments. Rovan et. al. [7] classify mapping schemes as one-to-one, divergent or convergent, suggesting that convergent mappings have higher potential for expressivity. Hunt and Kirk [8] carried out user studies with a multiparametric interface composed of a mouse and sliders, concluding that this class of interface can be beneficial to musicians, and also that mappings which are not one-to-one are more engaging.

In the area of timbre space navigation, evolutionary methods (e.g. [9]) have been well researched. Using interactive evolution, synthesis patches are encoded as individuals in a larger population and evolved with genetic techniques to navigate the search space. Although effective, these tech-

Figure 1. Phalanger in use

niques suffer from the bottleneck of human evaluation of fitness, which reduces the efficiency of the process. Seago et. al. [10] explored timbre space navigation, proposing two strategies, multidimensional line search and the use of adapted bayesian filters. A controller-based approach is taken by van Nort and Wanderley [11], who used a graphics tablet and mapping engine to navigate complex sonic spaces.

This project fits between these areas, applying multiparametric controllers to the problem of timbre space navigation. The development of the system will now be described, starting by introducing the controllers.

4. TWO MULTIPARAMETRIC CONTROLLERS

These controllers afford two styles of interaction: tangible, through the manipulation of malleable material, and intangible, through computer vision based hand tracking. Although they differ in these terms, from the point of view of the data they output they are very similar; both systems output a continuous multiparametric stream of data, in which, due to the physical nature of the devices, the parameters are codependent. Both of these systems were developed using the OpenFrameworks¹ C++ toolkit on Mac OS X.

4.1 A Hand Tracking Interface

The Phalanger interface is a computer vision based hand tracking system. It's a markerless system, so no wearables are required to use it, instead neural network based skin colour tracking is used to differentiate the hand from the background. Having separated out the hand, algorithms from the openCV² library are employed to analyse the geometry of the hand shape; these parameters (listed in table 1) can be streamed to other applications for continuous control. Another layer of the system tracks hand shape using Support Vector Machines, however this is not used in this project; instead the streams of hand geometry data are used for timbre space navigation. For hardware, the system uses a low-cost Sony PS3Eye USB camera at 320x240

¹ <http://www.openframeworks.cc/>

² <http://sourceforge.net/projects/opencvlibrary/>

1	Coordinates of the topmost point
2	Coordinates of the leftmost point
3	Coordinates of the rightmost point
4	Coordinates of the centroid of the hand
5	The angle of the hand
6	The area of the hand

Table 1. Hand geometry data

resolution. The camera is mounted on a retort stand; in this case the camera is positioned to point down at the hand on a desktop.

4.2 Malleable Foam

The EchoFoam controller, an increment to the design previously described in [1], is a malleable foam controller designed with the aim of enabling nuanced and intuitive musical control. The device is constructed from conductive foam, and exploits the property that this material changes electrical resistance when deformed, in order to track the shape of the foam. Rather than using separate sensors, the controller is made from one continuous piece of foam, with embedded contact wires measuring the resistances between different points. The controller is constructed from foam squares that are glued together into a cube. Contact wires are placed in the top and bottom squares, in the four corners and in the centre. These two sets of wires are connected to two separate 74HC4051 (de)multiplexer chips on a circuit board controller by an Arduino³. The two sets are divided into live and sensor wires; a program on the Arduino sequences the (de)multiplexers so that a single wire is made live on one side of the foam while the five wires on the other side are scanned to measure resistance between these contacts and the live point. In this way, ten contacts can be used to take twenty-five resistance readings from the foam. These measurements, in combination, provide a consistent signature describing the shape of the foam in any particular state of deformation. Figure 2 shows the controller in use.

This system is tightly coupled with the use of Echo State Networks (ESNs), which are used as mapping engines to create control streams from the foam sensor data.

5. MAPPING WITH ECHO STATE NETWORKS

ESNs are a class of recurrent neural network, belonging under the banner of *Reservoir Computing techniques* [12, 13]. They can be trained to approximate arbitrary dynamical systems, making them very useful tools for the temporal processing of multiparametric data streams, such as the outputs from EchoFoam and Phalanger. An ESN consists of a set of input and output nodes connected to a reservoir of interconnected nodes. Figure 3 shows a simplified example of ESN topology, in practice the central reservoir would be much larger. To train an ESN, a training set is created of inputs and outputs which demonstrate the desired behaviour of the trained system. During training, the

Figure 2. The Malleable Foam Controller In Use

Figure 3. An Example ESN

output weights are adjusted to exploit the dynamics of the reservoir and achieve the desired behaviour. Because only the outputs weights are adjusted, training is a linear problem which is fast to solve and makes ESNs convenient and reliable to use.

In this project, ESNs are used for dimensionality reduction and as a form of mapping engine. Given the interdependent nature of the output of the foam controller, ESN mapping is a fundamental part of this system; the data from Phalanger differs because the parameters can be considered independently, however for consistency and also for the purposes of dimensionality reduction, ESNs were used to map this data as well. For each controller, their output streams are passed through an ESN and reduced in number to match the number of parameters of the synthesis engine being controller. The training process to achieve this results in an arbitrary mapping, but the outputs change consistently for each potential set of inputs to the ESN, making them reliable for musical control. Figure 4 shows an example of the inputs and outputs of an ESN being used for dimensionality reduction.

6. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The timbre navigation system consisted of a collection of different programs and modules. The programs that run with each controller exist as separate OpenFrameworks applications, so an overlay application was designed that could host the timbre search engine and be integrated with both pieces of software. Figure 5 shows an overview of how the system was setup. Ableton Live was chosen as the

³<http://arduino.cc>

Figure 4. Echo State Network Mappings

sound engine; the software communicated with Live using liveOSC⁴, an OSC/Python interface that runs as part of Live. This provides a convenient way for the timbre navigation system to query the amount, type and ranges of synthesis parameters in Live, and automatically assign control streams to them.

7. EXPLORING TIMBRE NAVIGATION STRATEGIES

What we have already is the input from two different controllers, both of which can control an arbitrary number of parameters in an arbitrary way. With the foam, the user explores the parameter space by deforming its shape, and with the hand tracker the user can manipulate parameters by moving and changing the shape of their hand. In both cases, the sound will change in direct relation to body movement. When controlling larger subsets of the parameter space, small motions amount to very large timbre changes, so in terms of controllability, working in a smaller subset is better for fine tuning of the sound. This means some kind of strategy for moving and narrowing the subset is required. Both controllers also output codependent parameters, which means that with direct mapping it will not always be possible to reach every available timbre, so a strategy is required to compensate for this.

A timbre navigation engine was designed with these issues in mind, the development of which is now described. The development took place over three progressively more complex scenarios. Overall, a *blackbox* approach was used; the system was designed with the aim of controlling any synthesis process with continuously controllable parameters, purely with controllers and no GUI.

7.1 Scenario 1: A Four Dimensional Timbre Space

The control streams were mapped to four parameters of a virtual analog synthesiser. For this scenario, the core of the navigation process was designed. To create variable subsets within which to explore with the controllers, each controlled parameter was assigned upper and lower bounds to create a working range, and also a polarity to determine if the mapping would be inverted. Pressing a key on the

⁴<http://livecontrol.q3f.org/ableton-liveapi/liveosc/>

Figure 5. System Architecture

keyboard randomised these ranges and polarities, creating random areas of the timbre space to explore. The next step was to facilitate control of the subsets, to allow gradually refined navigation through the space. To achieve this, firstly a global percentage multiplier was applied to each range, so that the ranges could be narrowed around their center points. A continuous MIDI controller was mapped to this. Secondly, a mechanism was introduced to move the center of the ranges; pressing a key on the keyboard caused the ranges to center on the current value of each parameter, allowing navigation through the space. With these functions, the workflow for navigating the parameter space was as follows:

1. With the ranges set at full, explore different random subsets of the timbre space until something in the area of the desired result is found
2. Center on the area of the desired sound and zoom in a little by shrinking the working ranges
3. Explore the new ranges, getting closer again to the desired sound
4. Repeat the last two steps until the final result is reached

One issue was that using uniform randomness to determine the ranges sometimes led to tiny ranges on one parameter, limiting the scope of exploration. To remedy this, the random number generator was mapped through a sigmoid curve, making larger ranges more probable.

Figure 6 shows an example of how a four dimensional timbre space might be navigated. Each column represents a synthesis parameter, the shaded boxes represent the working range for that parameter and the + or - indicates mapping polarity. In (a) and (b), different random ranges are trialed to reach a suitable setting to start refining from. In (c) the ranges are re-centered and in (d) they are scaled

Figure 6. Exploring A Timbre Space

down. In (e) and (f), centering and scaling is repeated, arriving at a small subset of the possible space.

Overall, this solution worked satisfactorily for navigating this smaller timbre space, so the next challenge was to try exploring more dimensions.

7.2 Scenario 2: A Ten Dimensional Timbre Space

The system was mapped to ten parameters across two plugins, a sampler and a chorus that processed the sampler's output. With this amount of parameters, the process still seemed to work effectively. Up to this point, each output from the controller was mapped to the same parameter on the synthesiser. However, given the nonlinear nature on the controllers, each output stream behaves differently from another so this may limit the extent of the search space which can be navigated. To solve this, when the ranges were randomised, the parameter targets for each output stream were now randomised as well. To enable further control for the navigation process, code was added to enable mutation; pressing a key on the keyboard caused gaussian randomness between -10% and 10% to be added to the bounds of the ranges, allowed subtle variations in the exploration space. The addition of these new features helped further improve the control over navigation. The next scenario to explore was the case of when a synth had more parameters than could be reasonably output from the controllers.

7.3 Scenario 3: A Forty Dimensional Timbre Space, Navigated With 10 Control Streams

The VOPM⁵ softsynth was chosen for this scenario, an FM synthesiser with over forty parameters; forty of these were selected for control by the navigation engine. This was an interesting challenge as it involved nonlinear control of a highly nonlinear soundspace, and also because FM suffers from difficulty in mapping between gestural input and synthesis parameters [14]. At first this scenario seemed to produce no sound on many settings, it was found that this silence was caused by one key parameter when the value was above 20%, so this parameter was removed from the set of targets.

As there were less control streams than parameters to control, the target parameters were selected as a random subset of the available targets, and could be changed again randomly by pressing a key on the keyboard. Selecting a new random set of targets left the previous targets on the values they were at when the settings changed, so each new random jump navigated further through the timbre space. The nonlinear nature of this timbre space meant that some settings were silent or would jump very suddenly to a different sound, so a one level undo function was added enabling the user to jump back from an unwanted setting. Navigating through a larger set of target parameters with random target selection in this manner allowed each new setting to be explored in an embodied way with the controllers, and rejected with the undo function if the new set of targets didn't take the user in the right direction. To widen the search options further, a function was added to randomise the ranges of the currently selected targets while preserving the unselected ones.

8. INITIAL REACTIONS

The system is yet to undergo formal user evaluation, however some initial thoughts about the system were gathered from two musicians. During both interviews, debugging information was showing on the screen at the start; both musicians found the experience to be much improved with the visuals removed so they could concentrate on the controller. Most importantly, both musicians found the system engaging to use. Both preferred the hand tracker as the controller, finding it easy to keep points of reference. One attempted to navigate from a distorted sound to a clean sound and back again, and achieved this successfully. They found that with the hand tracker they could return consistently to a previous point in the timbre space, and felt that their ability to do this would improve with practice.

One issue was with using the range centering process; when the working ranges are moved to a new centre, the position on the controller now corresponds to a new position in the parameter space so the sound changes. This can disrupt the flow of navigating the search space, as it's sometimes difficult to find where the sound you had centered on is in the new search space, although it should always be possible to find it. Another issue was with the size

⁵ http://www.geocities.jp/sam_kb/VOPM/

of ranges, one interviewee felt it would be better to always start from much wider ranges or a completely full range.

9. DISCUSSION

The initial reactions demonstrate that the system can work successfully, although some refinement is needed. The main issue is the interaction between the range centering process and the current state of the controller, strategies need to be found to smooth out this process which in turn will improve the flow of the navigation experience. Another issue was widening the random range selection, this could be solved by providing MIDI control of the sigmoid curve which maps the random range values; the user could determine how likely ranges were to be large.

One interviewee commented that the system was good for making broader adjustments to the sound, but really fine adjustment was difficult; bearing this in mind it's interesting to consider where this type of system fits into the composition and editing process. Gelineck and Serafin [5] observe that musicians need more accurate control when they come to the final stages of a composition, so this system would fit in best at the earlier stages of creative exploration. Any settings discovered with the system can be fine tuned with a mouse and GUI later.

In terms of control, an interesting property of the system is the use of randomness; random values are used to move around the search space in search of a good place to begin fine-tuning parameters. This is necessitated by the blackbox approach to parameter control and also by the nature of the controllers. To determine mappings by something other than randomness, for example manual control, would require the attachment of meaning to variables in the system in relation to the sound being controlled, however given the embodied nature of the controllers, meaning in this system is derived from listening and physical interaction in an explorative process. Considering this, using randomness seems to be the most appropriate approach, although varying the type of randomness, for example with sigmoid mapping, can increase the level of control.

An interesting aspect of this system is the role of bimanual hand use. Treadaway [4], discussing hand use in creative practice, describes how in manual activities the dominant hand is used for micrometric and internally driven actions while the non-dominant hand is used for macrometric and externally driven actions, reflecting differences between the left and right brain hemispheres. This pattern of hand use is echoed with this system, one hand being employed for detailed exploration of the sound space while the other controls meta-level search parameters.

Returning to the questions posed in the introduction, on the issue of whether this system can plug in to any continually controllable synthesis process, this would seem possible but with one reservation that the parameters may need careful selection. In any synthesis engine, as observed in the FM synthesis scenario, there are certain parameters (for example master volume) that hold significance over others and should be excluded in a timbre space search. Parameter selection also depends on the intended sequencing of the sound, for example including envelope attack in the

search space for a sound played as staccato would not be relevant. Setting the initial target parameters is something that could be controlled by a GUI, and is part of the wider creative search process.

Two questions in the introduction concerned the comparison of the two controllers used with the system and also the comparison of the system with conventional control methods; there is not enough data to answer these yet, and a formal user evaluation will help to find some answers.

10. CONCLUSION

A system has been presented for the exploration of timbre spaces, that uses multiparametric controllers and an interactive search process to provide both low level and high level control over navigation. The search process uses a combination of techniques to progressively move and refine a subset of the full timbre space being explored until a desired setting is found. Initial reactions to the system have been encouraging, but more data is needed to evaluate the efficacy of the system. The next step in the project is a formal user study which will help to answer the questions posed earlier in the paper, and to improve the design of the system.

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